

APPENDIX A: End user interaction experiences

Air-quality

The air quality department (AQD) at our Agency covers the national network of surface stations. The correspondence with the department was quite regular and the first steps began when our remote sensing department (ARS) was doing market research. They were cooperating from the beginning of the project since the knowledge-based trigger to buy profilers came from their department.

Later on, as the project progressed, the topics of correspondence shifted from sensors to processing and applications, especially mixing layer height, fog and low winds. That said, it is very important to say that proactivity from the side of our remote sensing department (ARS) was of great importance to reach to the Air-quality department as soon as our knowledge on the subject increased and we could present the subject more clearly.

As the Slovenia's capital city Ljubljana lies in the broad valley basin, and situations with fog are very common during winter time, the need for data during the fog events was emphasized. That is why sodar-rass technology was accepted for one of the instruments. Loudness of the sensor brought an additional problem, which we solved, finding the location away from the populated area. We found the location at the Waste disposal facility and based on one year of data we are satisfied.

The interest for the data varies over time and is more pronounced during winter season when the Air-quality department is concerned with pollution (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) which is influenced by surface inversions and 24h mixing layer height dynamics. Here also low winds in lower level are of interest.

What is also really important is the accessibility of the product. Even one click too much will avert the potential user from a daily use of the product.

Numerical weather prediction

NWP sector is very strong and important field in meteorology at the national level and is interested in usability of measurements of wind profiles, and to some extent also temperature.

Current size of the gbrs network in Slovenia provides opportunities for model verification at the location of the profiler, but no advanced sensitivity studies which would address data assimilation. That is where again PROBE and E-PROFILE provide important knowledge base for us to know what bigger Met Offices are doing in the field of data assimilation for their local area models and what are their results.

When data were given to NWP sector at our Agency, they started to play with it and they became familiarized with the data. So their interest for the gbrs data is rising.

The NWP department is now using the wind profiles data to validate the model.

General weather forecasting office

Daily weather forecasting office is one of the potential regular users, but there is still much to be done to implement the use of gbrs visualization products like ALC backscatter profiles with MLH and wind profilers into their daily routine. Being a part-time forecaster gives me the opportunity to more easily reach the colleagues forecasters.

Zoom hybrid session of regular daily weather forecasting meetings played also a big role, since bigger audience was present compared to the meetings carried out in physical form. In that way I could reach much broader audience, also from other fields, taking a minute or two to suggest that they can also look at ALC and wind profiles, explaining the basics repeatedly many times.

They showed most interest for fog or low stratus situations and also for warm front passages during cold season since the process takes long time for the warm upper air to displace the cold pools in the valleys and in the basins.

During the warm season there is an interest for thermodynamic instability information for assessing the potential for severe convection.

Another very important application is the potential for freezing rain which has already caused lots of damage in Slovenia. That could be achieved by using ALCs, like CL61 and SODAR-RASS with the aid of daily radiosounding. The time development of the warm layer could be assessed and compared to models.

Existing CL31 ceilometers in our surface synoptic network represent a potential to provide backscatter data national wide with little effort, the main work being switching to the right data telegram of the ceilometers and adapt the operational dataflow scheme.

Aviation weather forecasting office

Weather forecasting for aviation is another very important player in the end user community. They are very interested in fog forecasting, onset and dissipation. We are currently involved in one advanced products program, called PARAFOG v2 (IPSL), which is the algorithm for fog onset prediction. The product is of great importance to our aviation weather forecasting Office.

Layers of freezing droplets are also important. Wind shear near the surface is another important parameter and also upper air turbulence sensing was expressed as a need.

Like with general weather forecasting there is a need during the warm season for thermodynamic instability information for assessing the potential for severe convection.

The complexity of the aviation community and the ICAO regulations result in a slower process of implementation of possible end-user products and solutions for the aviation Met Office.

With the plan to upgrade the existing CL31s in our surface synop network, we will check the stability of using the CL31s as ALCs and not only as ceilometers.

In summer 2022, the big fires in Slovenia influenced the aviation traffic and encouraged aviation weather forecasting office to approach us with questions on how we could provide support in case of such events. We immediately presented them the operational platform run by E-PROFILE and explained that our goals in relation to our existing synop CL31 network will provide just what they want. Here again our Remote sensing department will need to invest in knowledge transfer from the international community, like PROBE and E-PROFILE, to disseminate to the end-users the know-how of backscattering profiles interpretation regarding aerosol classification in case of fires or volcanic eruptions.

Municipalities

The municipality of Ljubljana is interested in providing the people with air-quality data. So that is where we would need an intermediate actor that understands how the local politics works and also the technicalities of the gbrs networks, data products and possible applications. It must also

possess the knowledge of how to communicate to the policy makers at the regional level. The gbrs products could provide important information for urbanization plans. We are still looking for an intermediate player to bridge the gap.

Another possible application we are considering is to provide the people with daily urban weather, air-quality conditions and thermal stress.

Waste disposal facility

We have a very good experiences with the Waste disposal facility in the suburbs of the capital of Ljubljana. They have also historical experiences with sodar measurements in the 90', but afterwards profile measurements stopped. The measurements were done by an external company which still exists and provides in-situ meteorological measurements at the location of the facility.

Our sodar-rass system was placed in the enclosed area of the Waste disposal facility where we have found an appropriate place away from populated areas and we are very satisfied with the operation of the system and the data.

The potential for accessing the mixing layer height (MLH) and also low winds in the surface layer is the application we see as the most appropriate. Currently they are only interested in wind profiles with the outside contracting company doing the visualization, but considering possible black scenarios of a fire or some pollutant escaping into the air, which is where additional information of MLH would be important.

Energetics

The private sector of energetics is very consistent and professional in their work. They know exactly what they want and they don't leave much room for vaguely defined products and solutions. They need final solutions and lots of marketing for persuasion. Maybe if energetic sector in bigger countries accepted some of the solutions based on the gbrs products then smaller countries could follow through well documented examples or through international organizations embracing some gbrs product solutions and promoting them among their members.

Possible product application that we as a Remote Sensing Department have recognized is forecasting of fog or low stratus duration since that is one of the inputs for the decision making on the daily energy needs for heating in the cold season for municipalities of bigger cities that have thermal plants.

There is also the need for assessing environmental impact of power plants, like waste burning power plants, since potential locations for plants are mostly in complex terrain or populated areas. Here the question about inversion heights or height of the mixing level is raised and also daily dynamics of the inversions.

The other interesting field in energetics is windfarming, but at the moment the green wind industry is still in a developing stage in Slovenia. In my opinion future will bring wind farms also to Slovenia and long term climatological data of wind and temperature stratification will be of great value.

Sport events

Sporting sector is another interesting end user. We have very good experiences with the hot-air balloon sector. We have provided them with real-time data of wind profilers during the World cup hot-air balloon competition in Slovenia in September 2022.

Hot-air balloon is also touristic branch that experienced great losses in recent years because of a few very big accidents.

The need for wind profiles data was clearly expressed from their side.

Another sport sector is ski jumping which is also very much dependent on the wind conditions. There the in-situ sensor network is already well implemented but we have been discussing the option of using a doppler lidar during the event to assess potential benefits.

Industry

The plant industry sector as such has not yet really embraced the green agenda for air-quality. So the regulatory standards and laws are the ones that push the industry to monitor and obey environmental standards.

Private companies are providing environmental monitoring in the field of air-quality for plants but that is a pretty non-objective approach. Current measurements are done in-situ with well accepted technology and sensors for temperature, wind and humidity. There is opportunity to provide profilers to better assess the stability classes and validate the dispersion models results for complex terrain situations.

Nuclear power plants

Strict regulations being part of nuclear power plant sector imply the need for a reliable and proved measurement technologies for providing time series of wind and temperature profiles. Those data serve as input for dispersion modeling that must be available at any time in case of accidents.

Some nuclear power plants are using measuring towers and others are using sodar-rass data. The use of an ALC lidars for MLH and Doppler lidars may be discussed but currently we have not addressed that industry sector.

Private companies in the field of environmental monitoring and modeling

There are many private companies working in the field of environmental monitoring and modeling.

They provide on demand environmental monitoring or modeling for different companies in the industry sector.

We have reached out to some of them and one company responded as they have experiences with sodar measurements. It might be a fruitful cooperation in the future.

Faculty and academia

Academia and institutes have a very different "modus operandi" compared to public Agencies so common interests must be identified. From the viewpoint of national Agency, we should look at the cooperation as an investment, since this is a possibility to attract young scientists and researchers that could later work at the Agency.

We have reached out to two universities, one in Ljubljana and one in Nova Gorica. They both offer programs in physics and meteorology. The second one is also hosting a "Center for atmospheric research" where they have a polarization Raman lidar and an elastic-fluorescent lidar. They work on projects of Bora wind measurements and modeling, aerosol classification and stratospheric measurements, providing also the opportunities for student diplomas, masters and doctorates. We are in the process of defining our potential future cooperation.

The possibility of reaching out to students is very limited since the number of students in the field of meteorology is very small, so we have expanded our field of view and we are considering the whole spectrum of physics and environmental sciences.